

In-Betweenness in Graphs

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Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet habe.

Kiel,

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Abstract

The world of Graph Mining treats nodes as binary - either they are of interest for what we are about to do, or they are outliers. In this thesis we propose a third option: what if there are some outliers that hold vital information about the cluster of nodes we are focusing on, while also acting as a link to other clusters in the underlying structure, acting as in-between instances and opening up a plethora of new information about the data we are working with? In order to broaden our views regarding this topic, in this theoretical work we set out to analyse different approaches of extracting clusters from graphs to identify whether they hold potential of being capable to do this job - identifying outliers as well as identifying multiple overlapping communities and therefore aiding us in the task of finding in-between instances. And, if they fall short of this task, how one could potentially modify them in order to gain this information.

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Introduction

1.1 Motivation

It is reasonable to say that Graph Mining is among the most well-researched subjects in Computer Science, presenting a plethora of different approaches and use-cases on a variety of different graphs. Edges can be weighted or unweighted, the graphs themselves either subgraphs - part of a larger graph - or on their own, nodes either are or are not labeled.

Two of the most prevalent research topics in this already extensively researched field are clustering; the search for well-linked communities, and outlier detection. Bar a fair few, every algorithm working on any type of graph deals with either one or both of these topics in some form or another, approaching the subject from a variety of different angles. However, they all have something in common: outliers get discarded on a regular basis, the respective nodes being of no further interest for the upcoming processes and evaluations, demonstrated in, among others, a paper by [Pandhre et al. (2016)], where one of the mentioned use-cases for outlier detection is to de-noise the network data, thus making it more manageable.

But what is an outlier from a semantic point of view, especially in the context of graphs and, in more detail, community search? Are all outliers the same, can we differentiate between different types of outliers, or are all outliers of equally little information to the network or dataset we are interested in? What if some outliers actually hold information pertinent to the data sets we are interested in?

These albeit simple questions are not as easy to answer as it might seem at first glance, however outliers seem to appear in every single well-researched topic and field of data and graph mining. Almost all algorithms published in this field and regularly used have some form of handling data points and nodes they deem of little informational value to the underlying task. But what if in doing so, they also discard points that are of high informational and strategic value to the knowledge we can discover from a network?

In this work we present the concept of in-betweeners - nodes that traditionally get discarded as outliers because of their position in the network being the one between either two separate knowledge graphs or between different node clusters in a single graph, building a bridge between two previously not linked structures. A similar concept, although for single points of data, not for a graph network, has been described by [Kazempour et al. (2024)] as follows: "There exists a special type of instances that are characterized by their property to connect clusters, by acting as a (semantic) conduit between groups. [...] They share certain traits from two or more neighbouring classes, acting as potential connectors." Their work however, putting a strong focus on the detection and formalisation of in-between instances in non-linked data sets, does not elaborate on how to discover or formalise these instances in a graph setting and what unique implications and challenges it holds.

In their paper regarding the Minimum Wiener Connector Problem, [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] already made steps towards identifying the strategic positioning and value of in-betweeners, stating "These [edges of a graph that bridge different communities] also have strategic importance: information has to go over these bridges to propagate from a community to others, thus the vertices incident to bridges

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enjoy a strategically favorable position because they can block information, or access it before other individuals in their community", and later on also declare "they are the best candidates to target for blocking the spread of rumors or viral diseases in a social network, or the spread of malware in a network of computers" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)].

While the prior work mentioned so far addresses the topic of in-betweenness, it also provides space for emerging questions such as: what are potential semantics for in-betweenness? Similar to clustering where there is not *the one* underlying clustering model (variance minimizing, density-based, spectral etc.), there can be different archetypes of in-betweenness on graphs and, accompanied with them, different ways to discover them. Since this type of pattern has not been coined with the term in-between instances in previous works, it is of non-trivial nature to discover such publications and hence finding different archetypes and algorithms to discover them. This work is dedicated in systematically classifying existing algorithms that address the in-between instance detection task on graphs. The challenges that arise with this objective are manifold: what are the key terms that are semantically similar to in-betweeners? Do they actively look for such patterns or do they emerge as a 'by-product'? What are the assumptions made by different authors about discoveries we coin as in-between instances?

1.2 Preliminaries

1.2.1 Graphs, Edges and Nodes

1.2.1 Definition (Graphs). A **graph** $G = (V, E)$ is a mathematical structure consisting of two sets V and E . The elements of V are called *vertices* and the elements of E are called *edges*. Each edge has a set of one or two vertices associated to it, which are called its *endpoints*. [Zhang and Chartrand (2006)]

1.2.2 Definition (Vertex Set). A **vertex set** V is a set of objects $a, b, c, \dots, i, j, \dots$ called *vertices*. These are conventionally represented by labeled geometrical points in the plane. [Essam and Fisher (1970)]

1.2.3 Definition (Edges). An **edge** is an unordered pair of distinct vertices from a vertex set V . The edge (i, j) is said to be *incident* with the vertices i and j and to *connect* them. An edge may be represented by a continuous line connecting the points i and j . [Essam and Fisher (1970)]

1.2.4 Definition (Edge Set). An **edge set** E associated with a vertex set V is a set of edges with vertices in V . [Essam and Fisher (1970)]

1.2.5 Definition (Internal and external edges). We classify the edges incident of $v \in C$ into two groups: **internal** edges that connect v to other vertices also in C , and **external** edges that connect v to vertices that are *not* included in the cluster C .

$$\begin{aligned} deg_{int}(v, C) &= |\Gamma(v) \cap C| \\ deg_{ext}(v, C) &= |\Gamma(v) \cap (V \setminus C)| \\ deg(v) &= deg_{int}(v, C) + deg_{ext}(v, C) \end{aligned}$$

[Schaeffer (2007)]

1.2.6 Definition (Subgraphs). A **subgraph** of a graph G is a graph H whose vertices and edges are all in G . If H is a subgraph of G , we may also say that G is a *supergraph* of H . [Zhang and Chartrand (2006)]

1.2.7 Definition (Adjacency Matrix). Let G [be] a graph with n vertices $1, 2, \dots, n$. The adjacency matrix of G with respect to this particular listing of n vertices is the $n \times n$ matrix and denoted by $X(G)$ and

defined as

$$X(G) = [x_{ij}] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } v_i, v_j \text{ is an edge, i.e. } v_i \text{ is adjacent to } v_j \\ 0, & \text{if there is no edge between } v_i \text{ and } v_j \end{cases}$$

1.2.8 Definition (Undirected Graph). The graph G is said to be **undirected** if $(i, j) \in E$ implies $(j, i) \in E$ and $a_{i,j} = a_{j,i}$. Thus, a graph will be undirected if and only if its adjacency matrix is symmetric. We use the term *undirected edges* to refer to a pair of edges between two nodes [...] with equal weight. [Young et al. (2016)]

1.2.9 Definition (Weighted Graph). In a **weighted graph**, a weight function $\omega : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined that assigns a weight on each edge. [Schaeffer (2007)]

1.2.10 Definition (Weighted Networks). The weight of the links between nodes are described by an $N \times N$ matrix $W = \{w_{ij}\}$. The weight $\{w_{ij}\}$ is 0 if the nodes i and j are not linked. [...] The statistical parameters for weighted networks are defined as follows: The node degree $k_i = \sum_{j \in \Pi(i)} a_{ij}$, which is the number of links attached to a node i , is extended directly to the strength or weighted degree, which is the sum of the weights of all links attached to node i :

$$s_i = \sum_{j \in \Pi(i)} w_{ij}$$

[Antoniou et al. (2008)]

1.2.11 Definition (Weighted Conductance).

$$\phi(w)(C, G) = \frac{W_{cut}(C)}{WVol(C)} = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in E, i \in C, j \in V \setminus C} w(i, j)}{\sum_{i \in C} \sum_{j, (i,j) \in E}$$

with $WVol(C)$ being the total weighted degree of nodes in C [Perozzi et al. (2014)]

1.2.12 Definition (Network Efficiency).

$$\mathcal{E}(G) = \frac{1}{|V|(|V| - 1)} \sum_{u, v \in V, u \neq v} \frac{1}{d_G(u, v)}$$

[Ruchansky et al. (2017)]

1.2.13 Definition (Network Inefficiency).

$$\mathcal{I}(G) = \sum_{u, v \in V, u \neq v} 1 - \frac{1}{d_G(u, v)}$$

[Ruchansky et al. (2017)]

1.2.14 Definition (wiener Index).

$$W(H) = \sum_{\{u, v\} \subseteq V(H)} d_H(u, v)$$

1.2.15 Definition (Minimum Wiener Index).

$$H^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{G[S]: S \subseteq V} \sum_{\{u, v\} \in S} d_{G[S]}(u, v)$$

with $G[S]$ denoting a subgraph induced by a set of nodes S and $d_{G[S]}(u, v)$ denoting the shortest path distance between the nodes u and v [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]

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1.2.16 Definition (Cuts). A partition of the vertices V of a graph $G = (V, E)$ into two nonempty sets S and $V \setminus S$ is called a **cut** and is denoted by $(S, V \setminus S)$. A cut is uniquely identified by defining a set S ; hence any subset of V can be called a cut. As the sets S and $V \setminus S$ define the same cut, it is often preferred to denote by S the *smaller* set, hence requiring $|S| \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$.

The **cut size** is the number of edges that connect vertices in S to vertices in $V \setminus S$. [Schaeffer (2007)]

1.2.2 Outliers

Other than with all of the previously well-researched concepts and structures, there exists a huge variety of definitions regarding what can be classified as an outlier. For the sake of this work, we will be following the definition provided by Douglas M. Hawkins:

1.2.17 Definition (Outlier). An **outlier** is an observation which deviates so much from the other observations as to arouse suspicions that it was generated by a different mechanism [Hawkins (1980)]

1.2.3 Clusters

Similar to the problem we encountered regarding a unified definition concerning outliers, the same thing holds true for clusters in graphs. A globally accepted definition does not seem to exist, and whereas almost all literature agrees on the fact that clusters have to be connected, they differ in a lot of other parameters. Generally, the loosest definition of a graph cluster can be summarised as a *connected component*, with the strictest requirements in literature covered by the concept of a *maximal clique* [Schaeffer (2007)]. In the following we will be introducing both upper and lower limits for a cluster definition.

1.2.18 Definition (Connected Component). A graph is **connected** if for every pair of vertices u and v , there is a path from u to v [Zhang and Chartrand (2006)].

For a connected graph G , the *distance* $d(u, v) = d_G(u, v)$ between two vertices u and v is the length of the shortest path from u to v . [Hellwig and Volkmann (2008)]

1.2.19 Definition (Maximum Clique). Let $G = (V, E)$ be an undirected graph with vertex set $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ and edge set $E \subseteq V \times V$. A **clique** C of G is a subset of V such that every two vertices in C are adjacent, i.e., $\forall u, v \in C, \{u, v\} \in E$. A clique is **maximal** if it is not contained in any other clique. [Wu and Hao (2015)]

1.2.20 Definition (Intra-cluster Density). We refer to the density of the subgraph induced by the cluster as the **internal** or **intra-cluster** density:

$$\delta_{int}(C) = \frac{|\{\{v, u\} | v \in C, u \in C\}|}{C(|C| - 1)}$$

[Schaeffer (2007)]

1.2.21 Definition (Intercluster Density). The intercluster density of a given clustering of a graph G into k clusters C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k is the *average* of the intercluster densities of the included clusters:

$$\delta_{int}(G|C_1, \dots, C_k) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{int}(C_i)$$

[Schaeffer (2007)]

1.2.22 Definition (External or Inter-cluster Density). [...] is defined as the ratio of intercluster edges to the maximum number of intercluster edges possible, which is effectively the sum of the cut sizes of all the clusters, normalized to the range $[0, 1]$:

$$\delta_{ext}(G|C_1, \dots, C_k) = \frac{|\{\{v, u\} | v \in C_i, u \in C_j, i \neq j\}|}{n(n-1) - \sum_{l=1}^k (|C_l|(|C_l| - 1))}$$

1.2.4 Algorithms

For the basic definition of a Random Walk, we will be using the following direct definition provided by [Xia et al. (2020)]

1.2.23 Definition (Random Walk). A **random walk** is known as a random process. It describes a path consisting of a succession of random steps on some mathematical space, which can be denoted as $\{\zeta_t, t = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ where ζ_t is a random variable describing the position of a random walk after t steps. The sequence can also be regarded as a special category of Markov chain. In the initial state of a random walk, the position ζ_0 may be fixed or drawn from some initial distribution P_0 . We can represent the distribution of position after t steps as follows:

$$P_t(i) = Pr(\zeta_t = i)$$

where $P_t(i)$ is the probability that the random walk visits the position i after t steps. If the walk locates at the position i after t steps, the single step transition probability refers to the probability, that the random walk can move to the position j after the next step. It is represented as p_{ij} and can be calculated as:

$$p_{ij} = Pr(\zeta_{t+1} = j | \zeta_t = i).$$

Further, the t steps transition probability is defined as follows:

$$p_{ij}^{(t)} = Pr(\zeta_t = j | \zeta_0 = i)$$

1.2.24 Definition (Transition Matrix). Let \mathbf{P} represent the **transition matrix**, where $P(i, j)$ is the transition probability from node i to j , i.e., $P(i, j) = W(i, j) / \sum_{j \in V} W(i, j)$

1.2.25 Definition (Markov Chains). A **Markov chain** is [...] a collection of random variables $\Phi = \{\Phi_n : n \in T\}$, where T is a countable time set. It is customary to write T as $\mathbb{Z}_+ := \{0, 1, \dots\}$ [Meyn and Tweedie (2012)]

1.2.26 Definition (Random Walk with Restart (RWR)). In **Random Walk with Restart**, starting from a query node q , a single walker randomly explores the network. At each time point, the walker has a probability α ($0 < \alpha < 1$) to follow the transition probabilities in \mathbf{P} (see 1.2.24), and probability $(1 - \alpha)$ to jump back to q . Formally, we have

$$x^{(t+1)} = \alpha P^T x^{(t)} + (1 - \alpha)q$$

where $x^{(t)}$ is the node visiting probability vector at time t , and q is a vector with value 1 for the q -th entry and 0 for all others. [Bian et al. (2018)]

1.2.27 Definition (Memory-based Random Walk (MRW)). Given an undirected and connected graph $G = (V, E)$, we use \mathbf{W} to represent its adjacent matrix, where entry $W(i, j)$ is the weight of edge $(i, j) \in E$. Let \mathbf{P} represent the transition matrix, where $P(i, j)$ is the transition probability from node i to j , i.e. $P(i, j) = W(i, j) / \sum_{j \in V} W(i, j)$.

[...] in **MRW** we use a sliding window to memorize the key positions that the walker has previously

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visited and aggregate the entire visiting history of the walker. Moreover, the next step of the walker depends not only on the current node and q but also where the walker has visited. Specifically, in MRW we have

$$x^{(t+1)} = \alpha P^T x^{(t)} + (1 - \alpha)v^{(t)}$$

where $v^{(t)}$ represents the aggregated history of the previous steps.[Bian et al. (2018)]

All of the following definitions of various PageRank applications are cited from [Xing and Ghorbani (2004)]

1.2.28 Definition (Simplified PageRank). A [.] simplified version of PageRank is defined as:

$$PR(u) = c \sum_{v \in B(u)} \frac{PR(v)}{N_v}$$

where u represents a web page, $B(u)$ is the set of pages that point to u , $Pr(u)$ and $PR(v)$ are the rank scores of the pages u and v , N_v denotes the number of outgoing links of [a] page v [, and] c is a factor used for normalisation

1.2.29 Definition (PageRank).

$$PR(u) = (1 - d) + d \sum_{v \in B(u)} \frac{PR(v)}{N_v}$$

with d being a dampening factor, set to 0.85 in the original work, which can be understood as the probability of users following the actual link, whereas $(1 - d)$ can be regarded as the PageRank distribution from non-directly linked pages

Overview

To even reach the point of identifying outliers and in-between instances in graphs, one has to first begin with the task of graph clustering. As mentioned before in 1.2.3, finding a widely accepted and uniform definition of the meaning of the term itself as well as what can be accepted as the single best clustering algorithm does not exist, similar to clustering on vector data, where there is no single best clustering algorithm but a plethora of different methods, relying on different assumptions and hence, satisfying different objectives. However the survey paper by [Schaeffer (2007)] gives a good starting point and baseline. As the authors state, the universally understood goal of a clustering task is to divide the different nodes of a graph into two or more communities in such a way that all nodes ending up in the same cluster are either connected or fulfill some measure of similarity. Furthermore, a clustering algorithm of any type will produce clusters from any given graph [Schaeffer (2007)], no matter how many or even if the underlying graph structure shows any clusters to begin with. For that very reason, it is pertinent to not only rely on a generalised clustering approach, but to also have some quality measures in place to validate the clusters produced. It is not trivial to note that visualisation can be seen as a quality measure as well as the density of the induced subgraphs as well as the cut size, which can be understood as an isolation indicator for the emerging cluster: the smaller the cut size, the less external connections are present in between the subgraph and the remaining structure [Schaeffer (2007)].

Figure 2.1. Two graphs, one being a uniform random graph (l) and one having clearly clustered structures (r) with the same number of vertices and edges, but vastly different structures. [Schaeffer (2007)]

Matrix diagonalisation is an important application according to the authors of the aforementioned survey paper, as the resulting matrices can easily and efficiently be computed, which then opens the door for graph partitioning, with the goal of minimizing the edges crossing from one subgraph into another [Schaeffer (2007)]. Although the authors do not state it directly, it is implied here that those solutions that present the lowest number of subgraph-connecting edges are preferred, however this raises a question we are interested in:

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what if these crossing edges and the nodes they connect are of distinct importance to the information we can retrieve from the task of clustering?

The authors of the survey paper [Schaeffer (2007)] recognise this question later on and state that it is not always clear how to or if one even should assign a vertex fully to just one cluster or if it could instead have "levels of membership" in several different clusters and suggest the creation of a supercluster to handily bundle all of these overlapping clusters and vertices, at least for the task of document clustering.

One early attempt to not only observe disconnected clusters but in contrast to the previous understanding of clusters in the survey paper by [Schaeffer (2007)] to also witness their interconnectedness are so-called *caveman graphs*, which originate from social networks and aim to link various clusters, called "caves" in this context, together by having one edge from each cave point towards another cave in the underlying structure.

Figure 2.2. Examples of what is deemed a dense cluster of good quality, measured by its internal and external edges (left), a slightly worse cluster, since it has more external than internal edges (middle) and a bad cluster, that, although it barely has any external edges, also lacks interconnectedness internally (right) [Schaeffer (2007)]

Another early emerging group of clustering methods are *fuzzy clustering algorithms*, whose general aim is to model ambiguous unlabeled patterns efficiently [Baraldi and Blonda (1999)], utilizing a fuzzy edge-relation R and a "membership function μ_R ". Whereas the concept of fuzzy clustering has not reached widespread acceptance, extrapolating from the overall prevalence of this method in the literature, and use compared to other clustering techniques, it is here where one can find a base method for assigning multiple vertices to multiple clusters, based on the more relaxed criterion of membership function that is used in this approach [Schaeffer (2007)].

Whereas all the previously mentioned approaches and techniques operate on undirected graphs, there also exists a variety of clustering algorithms on directed ones. Different to undirected graphs, here the connections being drawn between vertices can be and often times are asymmetrical, which influences the adjacency matrix in a similar way. One example for this are scientific articles, where one paper certainly references a variety of other papers, however, they do not, in kind, link back to the previously mentioned paper, but cite and reference other sources. In their survey paper, [Schaeffer (2007)] refer to the well-known *PageRank algorithm* as one typical example in the field of clustering on directed graphs. Briefly explained, the PageRank algorithm assigns a measure of importance to every web page it is tasked with clustering, with those initial values being identical for all pages and states that a page becomes more important if it has important pages linking to it. This effect propagates through the entire network of linked documents until it finally converges.

Figure 2.3. Depicting the simplified version of PageRank, denoted by the fact that no visitors, depicted as numbers, of one of the initial pages (left) are lost on their way to the next page, denoted by the sum of all outgoing links being the same as the initial visitors of that page [Xing and Ghorbani (2004)]

Whereas the simplified version of the algorithm, explained in 1.2.28 and in Figure 2.3 does not account for the fact that users might choose to not follow the provided paths in the form of hyperlinks and would rather make their own decisions, the naive implementation of the PageRank algorithm 1.2.29 does take this into account and can be seen as more suitable to our tasks of finding in-between instances in graphs, since, even though [Xing and Ghorbani (2004)] does not refer to them as outliers in their works, one can easily come to the understanding that pages that are not directly linked to the previously existing set, yet get visited by a not trivial number of users regardless, can be understood as a special form of outliers.

Another approach to clustering worth mentioning is *divisive clustering algorithms*, which work with a hierarchical approach, recursively finding clusters in the graph. Two of the more widely spread algorithms of this approach are *Markov Chains* and, extended from them, *Random Walks*.

Random Walks are made up of random, progressive steps through a network, depending on a probability distribution with which each node has a chance to be visited outgoing from the one we are currently looking at. In general, the greater an association between two nodes is, the higher the chance that this node will be visited. [Xia et al. (2020)]. In general, a succession of random steps throughout the graph network is observed, after which the random walker stops at a position i , while the step progression is saved in the form of an ordered sequence through time [Xia et al. (2020)], which shows the connection between Markov Chains as denoted in 1.2.25. Here, again, we get the intrinsic impression that, in the scope of a random walk, it could happen that one vertex gets visited by, as an example, not only one, but multiple random walkers, which all map out distinctly different communities, yet overlap in some areas, easily visible in their visiting history, determining nodes that are in-between multiple communities.

With these baselines established and the first questions raised, in the following chapter we will now take a more in-depth look at a variety of papers and approaches that, even though oftentimes veiled under a different name, show the potential for the discovery of in-between instances, with some possibly even providing a starting point for the conceptualisation of methods and algorithmic approaches to even identify in-between nodes.

Contrasting View

In the following sections we will take a closer look at different promising approaches and what we consider the potential for the identification of in between instances, providing an in depth view into different algorithms that are well established as well as some adaptations that are not yet widely spread, however hold a lot of potential.

3.1 Determining Connectedness

In a paper proposing a *Memory-based Random Walk* method to detect local communities, [Bian et al. (2018)] state that the usual assumption for this task is that all query nodes belong to or are from the same community, a requirement the authors deem as too strict and contrast it to applications in the real world, where one cannot reliably know if this assumption holds true or even how many different communities there actually are. To identify the actual number of communities, [Bian et al. (2018)] introduce the aforementioned expansion on the well-known Random Walk algorithm, which was previously elaborated on in this paper, see 1.2.23. Their adaptation is due to the two key limitations of the normal random walk algorithm they identified: firstly, walkers getting "trapped" in their relative neighborhoods, since the naive implementation does not track the previously visited nodes, therefore opening up the potential for, in the most extreme case, a walker only ever oscillating between at worst two nodes [Bian et al. (2018)]. Secondly, according to the authors, individual walkers only ever map out the community in which they started and do not interact with other walkers.

Figure 3.1. Exemplary visualisation of how two different algorithms detect the communities associated with their respective nodes, depicting a version of the PageRank-Nibble algorithm on the left, and the Memory-based Random Walk on the right

As a solution, the authors are proposing a memory-based approach, that is simultaneously able to address both of their stated key challenges. Contrary to other algorithms, no assumptions are made about how many communities we could be dealing with. Their approach differs from the naive Random Walk implementation in two critical aspects: For one, the visiting history of each walker is recorded in the form of a score vector, more accurately this is achieved via the sliding window method

3. Contrasting View

in order to clearly depict the previous steps of the walker, which is then aggregated over the entire visiting history; and, based on their recorded visiting history, interactions between the walkers are introduced [Bian et al. (2018)]. Especially the concept of recording a walkers history is beneficial to us in the onset of the task of identifying in-between instances, since the recording of the visiting history for each walker later on leads to the possibility of comparing their visiting history in the form of similarity vectors, a topic on which we will elaborate in the next section of this chapter.

In order to record the visiting history, the previously mentioned score vectors are utilized, as walkers with a similar visiting history have the ability to mutually reinforce each other, which potentially removes the bias towards their own query nodes [Bian et al. (2018)].

Another paper we want to put our focus on in the scope of this work has been written by [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] and introduces a new form of measurement under the name of *network inefficiency*, which is being used to determine a *selective connector*. The selective connector is defined as a set of query vertices $Q \subseteq V$ in a graph $G = (V, E)$ that exhibits some cohesiveness property, but has less strict requirements in term of connectedness, which, according to [Ruchansky et al. (2017)], is to prevent the normal consequence that usually comes with strict connectedness requirements: the need to connect possibly unconnected vertices for the requirements' sake only, but in the aftermath leading to too large solutions. In addition to this, the authors also elaborate in the assumption made by a large amount of the literature - being that all vertices belong to the same target community. [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] state that, if this assumption holds, most algorithms deliver "reasonably compact subgraphs", but also explicitly state that this compactness falls apart and returns too large subgraphs if not all query nodes are part of the same community.

The prevalent topic of this paper is the study of what [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] coin as the *selective connector problem* - "given [the aforementioned graph and a set of query vertices,] find a superset $S \supseteq Q$ such that the induced subgraph, denoted as $G[S]$ has some good "cohesiveness" properties, but is not necessarily connected" [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]. In extension, the authors also define three further properties they deem desirable for their selective connector $G[S]$, that we will briefly summarise: 1) **Parsimonious vertex addition**: Only add vertices if and only if this helps to form a more cohesive subgraph by better connecting the vertices. 2) **Outlier tolerance**: If the query vertex set Q contains vertices that are far from the other vertices, those vertices should remain disconnected and considered as outliers. 3) **Multi-community awareness**: If the query vertices in Q belong to more than one community, the connector should be able to recognize this and detect the communities, while refraining to force a connectedness onto them [Ruchansky et al. (2017)].

Elaborating on what they understand as a good cohesiveness measurement, [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] focus on what they deem to be the natural way of cohesiveness by considering the shortest-path distance $d_{G[S]}(u, v)$ of every pair of vertices of the subgraph $G[S]$, denoting the importance of this measure as playing an important part in forming new communities as well as for the purpose of propagating information through a network. But with the shortest-path distance, issues arise as well: once the requirement for connectedness is not upheld or upheld strongly anymore, this also has the potential of removing the connection between two vertices u, v , returning an infinite shortest-path distance. As a workaround, [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] advocate for the use of the reciprocal shortest-path distance, since it handles such infinite distances well by following the convention that $\infty^{-1} = 0$. This workaround also is the basic idea behind measuring network efficiency, which can be summarised as "how efficiently can a network exchange information without much loss or misinformation". However, [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] express that defining their selective connector problem as finding a subgraph which maximises network efficiency is not feasible, since the normalisation factor $|V|(|V| - 1)$ of the equation presented in 1.2.12 has the potential to allow the addition of vertices with no relation to Q

in order to improve network efficiency, which stands in absolute contrast to the desired property of parsimonious vertex addition. As an alternative solution, [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] introduce what they call the measure of inefficiency of a subgraph 1.2.13 and specify their definition of the selective connector problem as the "parameter-free problem which requires extracting the subgraph $G[S]$, with $S \supseteq Q$, that *minimizes network inefficiency*." Based on this, now each vertex pair in the desired subgraph produces a cost set between 0 and 1, with it being minimal if the two vertices measured are neighbours and maximally large if the two vertices in focus cannot be connected in the graph, with the property of parsimony being handled by the "sum of costs over all pairs of vertices in the connector" [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] - the inclusion of a vertex only being worth it if the costs of adding it are small and if the addition in some way helps to reduce the total distance among the vertices in the subgraph S . More importantly for the scope of this work, following the now upheld criterion of parsimonious vertex addition, both of the other stated desired properties - the handling of outliers as well as the recognition of multiple communities - also directly follow out of the now relaxed connectedness requirement.

Figure 3.2. Example of the performance of three different algorithms - local discrepancy maximization (**ldm**), MDL-based (**mdl**) and the minimum inefficiency subgraph (**mis**) from left to right - on the Dolphin toy-graph with query vertices depicted in blue and added vertices in green [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]

3.2 presents three different algorithms that allow their solutions to be disconnected, yet with noticeably different outcomes. The leftmost approach, *local discrepancy maximization* (**ldm**) only returns one massive connected component as a solution, having no impact on its ability to handle outliers, however massively undermining its ability to recognise the existence of more than one community in the underlying structure of the graph. The *MDL-based* approach (**mdl**) on the other hand adds a bunch of superfluous vertices to the network, in this particular example even undermining its own ability to soundly identify and exclude outliers. The rightmost approach of the *minimum inefficiency subgraph* (**mis**), only adds one vertex per query vertex set, clearly distinguishing between the two communities and separating the outlier query vertex [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]. This is more in the sense of what we set out to do in this work, since it depicts a noticeable ability to identify more than one community in the underlying structure while still following the criterion of parsimonious vertex addition as to not make the solution space arbitrarily large.

The next paper we are analysing in the scope of this work is titled "Focused Clustering and Outlier Detection in Large Attribute Graphs", written by [Perozzi et al. (2014)], which approaches the problem of graph mining on large attribute graphs with the help of user preference, arguing that user guided

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decisions are of particular interest in this setting, since the users might only be interested in a very small set of the overall available attributes. This, according to the authors, also helps to obtain the most sought after solution, since control over the clustering process yields different solutions. In order to control this process, [Perozzi et al. (2014)] rely on "exemplar nodes" provided by the user from which an *attribute weight* is inferred. It is important to note that these weights are set by the users and are used as a measure of perceived similarity. The higher the inferred weight of an attribute, the more relevant it is to the user, with those of the highest weights being henceforth known as *focus attributes* [Perozzi et al. (2014)].

Figure 3.3. Example graph of clustering with the help of user-set focus attributes, clearly depicting two different clusters based on which attribute is deemed more important [Perozzi et al. (2014)]

As seen in 3.3, different clusters emerge depending on which of the four provided attributes - degree, location, mother tongue, occupation - are deemed more or less important than others. Whereas the left cluster emerges due to the degree and location of the exemplary nodes, the right cluster is formed due to similarities in occupation [Perozzi et al. (2014)], we will elaborate more on the outlier of the exemplary node set, as well as the possibility for in-betweenness that emerges from this graph in the next section of this work.

[Perozzi et al. (2014)] advise that it is very likely to extract a number of user-preferred clusters from each graph, and, following this finding, name three desired properties of an algorithm working with user preference and focus attributes: the algorithm has to 1) be able to effectively identify user preference, 2) have the capability to extract the relevant clusters locally without partitioning the entire graph and 3) be able to identify outliers [Perozzi et al. (2014)]. Furthermore the authors of the paper identify the unique contributions of their approach as, for one, introducing a user-oriented problem setting for attribute graphs with the goal of finding *focused* clusters and outliers based on *user preference*, and, secondarily, they propose an algorithm, named **FocusCO**, that has the capability to simultaneously extract the sought after clusters from large graphs and also identifies outliers reliably. [Perozzi et al.

(2014)] formalise their problem as follows:

"Given a large attributed graph $G(V, E, F)$ with $|V| = n$ nodes and $|E| = m$ edges, where each node is associated with $|F| = d$ attributes, extract from G only the [...] clusters pertaining to a user u 's interest" [Perozzi et al. (2014)]. One precursor to this task is that the user provides a number of exemplary nodes C_{ex} that are similar to the types of nodes the user wants in their final cluster. After this step and with the underlying assumption that nodes in a cluster are similar in a number of choice attributes, the next step is to infer weights β_u to the attributes as a measurement of defining the similarity between the nodes of the exemplary set provided by the user by utilizing the inverse Malahanobis distance with A as the identity matrix so it yields the Euclidian distance and f_i, f_j being the feature vectors of two nodes i, j ,

$$(f_i - f_j)^T A (f_i - f_j)$$

with the expected result being a sparse vector that only holds a few large weights for a chosen few attributes. In the following step, the focused cluster C is being extracted from the original graph G , with the requirement that the extracted clusters are presenting a dense structure and are reasonably well separated from the rest of the graph as can be seen in 3.9 and that the clusters are consistent regarding the focus attributes with large weights, eg. hold the attributes the user deems as of special interest [Perozzi et al. (2014)]. This is achieved by identifying reasonable candidate nodes from G that uphold the attribute requirements determined by the user and then in a next step expanding the search for even more good candidate nodes around those already identified in the previous step, following the intuition that nodes in focused clusters have a high weighted similarity to their neighbors [Perozzi et al. (2014)], resulting in the formation of connected components that the authors in this paper refer to as *core set*. After identifying these cores, the *FocusCO* algorithm expands around them, selectively picking out nodes to include in the connected component until it is impossible to add more nodes that would increase the quality of the cluster, which is measured in the form of conductance in the work of [Perozzi et al. (2014)], since this measurement takes both cut size and total volume and density of the emerging cluster into account. Candidate nodes are taken from the neighbors of nodes already included in the cluster, and then, for each non-member node, the difference in cluster conductance is calculated that would arise from that nodes' inclusion. This decision happens greedily, so as a followup step, the *FocusCO* algorithm checks if conductance of the cluster would improve if it were to remove any node. These steps of addition and removal get repeated until convergence.

The authors note that it is absolutely possible for focused clusters to be overlapping in several nodes, a pattern following real-world networks from a range of topics. Additionally noteworthy is that the focused cluster C can, and realistically often is a subset of all clusters in G . This effect emerges since, according to [Perozzi et al. (2014)] "different sets of clusters are expected to unite around different attributes and we aim to extract only those that are specifically similar to the type of clusters user u is interested in." Regarding outliers, the authors define them in the scope of their work as structurally belonging to a focused cluster, but showing some deviation from other cluster members in their focus attributes, which can easily be seen in the previously provided figure 3.9 if one directs their attention to the exemplary node colored in red in the left cluster.

To quantify their definition of outliers - nodes that structurally belong to a cluster with regards to their connection to other nodes but deviate in some focus attribute from other cluster members - [Perozzi et al. (2014)] introduce the term of *BSN* - best structural nodes in terms of unweighted conductance. Nodes of this type get identified during the expansion around the core sets and, once convergence of a focus cluster is reached, compared to the BSNs actually included in that cluster, as those are the nodes understood as focused outliers in this work.

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The next paper we are examining in this work is again written by [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] and is dealing with finding a *minimum Wiener connector*, expanding on work done by Harry Wiener with the task of finding a subgraph that connects all query vertices while presenting a minimum Wiener Index. The authors define the term *connector* as the subgraph H of a graph $G = (V, E)$ with a set of query vertices $Q \subseteq V$ that "explains" the connections of the nodes in the underlying graph Q , leading to the strong requirement that H has to be connected and also hold all of the query vertices in Q . According to [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] many other methods that exist in literature make the implicit assumption that all query vertices of Q belong to the same resulting community and that a "good solution" will also contain other nodes. If these assumptions are decently satisfied, the authors state that those methods then also yield reasonably good solutions in the form of subgraphs. However if the condition that all query vertices belong to the same community fails, e.g. if the vertices are spread over multiple communities in the input vertex set Q , those methods return subgraphs of unnecessarily large size, often times rendering them "meaningless and unusable" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)].

The authors [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] state their goal as the following: finding a small connector, defined by them as a connected subgraph that contains all of the query vertices in Q , as well as a *small* set of additional vertices, as these "could explain the relation among the vertices in Q , or could participate in some function by acting as important links among the vertices in Q " [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]. This small set of additional vertices in the connector is of particular interest to us in the scope of this paper, since it bears a lot of similarities to our understanding of in-between instances.

They continue to formalise their problem as, given a graph $G = (V, E)$, and a set of query vertices $Q \subseteq V$, find a connector H^* that minimises the sum of shortest path distances among all pairs of vertices in the solution following the formula given in 1.2.15. This is, according to the authors, of special importance since shortest path distances "define fundamental structural properties of graphs, playing a role in all the basic mechanisms of networks such as their evolution and the formation of communities" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)], which, again, is on par with what we are looking for in the search of good methods and algorithms that have a potential of identifying in-between instances in graphs. Additionally, [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] add the importance of *betweenness centrality*, defined as the fraction of shortest paths a vertex is a part of, stating that it is a measurement of great import of any vertex, as it is a measure for identifying the extend to which "an actor" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] controls the flow of information through the network.

Figure 3.4. Exemplary depiction of two minimum Wiener connectors, performed on the "Karate Club" data set. Note that the query vertices (dark grey) on the lefthand side belong to different communities, whereas the ones on the right belong to the same community [Ruchansky et al. (2015)].

To exemplify the concept of a minimum Wiener connector, reference 3.4. In this example, a section of the larger Karate Club social network is depicted, Here, another theory by [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] becomes visible: they state that if all query vertices, coloured dark grey in the image provided, belong to the same community, the nodes added to form the minimum wiener connector will also more likely than not belong to that same community, and are likely to be "influential vertices", portraying a higher centrality than the initial query vertices belonging to Q . Furthermore, if the vertices do not belong to the same community as is the case in the left part of the image, [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] state that the additional vertices needed to form the connector will "contain vertices adjacent to edges that bridge the different communities", which is on par with our understanding of what an in-between instance is and what it can be used for - bridging communities that have some semblance of belonging together and being the vertices that craft this connection. These vertices are of great import, as stated by [Ruchansky et al. (2015)], since information has to go over those bridges in order to reach new communities, based on its point of origin.

[Ruchansky et al. (2015)], defining their problem as finding subgraphs that connect a given set of query vertices while also minimising the Wiener index, state that there exists a "proper tradeoff" between it portraying small pairwise distances *and* using few vertices, since adding vertices, although it may decrease the overall distances, leads to an increased number of terms that have to get summed up in 1.2.14. This, at first glance, might show resemblance to the well-known Steiner tree problem, briefly summarised as given a graph G and a set of terminal vertices Q of G , find a minimum sized connector for Q . But they are in fact different problems, with what constitutes as an optimal solution for a Steiner Tree sometimes being an arbitrarily bad solution as a minimum Wiener connector [Ruchansky et al. (2015)].

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Figure 3.5. Example of a case where a Steiner Tree solution exhibits an arbitrarily large Wiener index [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]

To exemplify this, we reference 3.5. Here, the set of $Q = v_1, \dots, v_n$ resembles our query vertices or, in the case of Steiner Trees, terminal vertices. The optimal solution in the case of a Steiner Tree would be the structure of Q itself, resembling a Wiener index $W(H)$ of 165. However an addition of either one of the root vertices r_1 or r_2 would lower the Wiener index to 151 in either case, with the optimal solution being the addition of both root vertices to Q , with $W(Q \cup \{r_1, r_2\}) = 142$. This is easily explained by the fact that the Steiner Tree problem "seeks connectors with as few edges/vertices as possible" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)], which is a big hindrance in the pursuit of small pairwise distances.

3.2 The Notion of In-Between Instances

The first algorithm by [Bian et al. (2018)] we have discussed in the previous section is the method of finding communities with the help of a Memory-based Random Walk algorithm, that utilizes a sliding window to capture previous key visiting positions of a walker and aggregate them over the entire history with the help of score vectors, that also hold as a tool of introducing interactions between various random walkers based on their score vector similarity.

Figure 3.6. Depiction of the cosine similarity of three respective walkers, belonging to the nodes 1 - 3 seen in 3.1. This underlines the strong notion that points 1 and 2 belong to the same community, given their very strong cosine similarity score [Bian et al. (2018)].

3.2. The Notion of In-Between Instances

But what we can also gather from 3.6, which is depicting the cosine similarity of the score vectors of the nodes 1 - 3 that we have already seen in 3.1, and especially under the influence of that figure, is the fact that up to a certain point, all 3 similarity vectors and, as an extension of that, all 3 score vectors seem to have a reasonably high degree of similarity between them. So the assumption, that all of the three walkers the score vectors are based on have at one point interacted with each other, is not only a reasonable, but also a founded one.

It is here that we see a big chance for the identification of in-between instances. In order to identify them, we are not reliant on perfectly matched cosine similarity vectors between two nodes, but rather are looking for a distinct peak, symbolising a strong alignment of two walkers over a certain amount of steps, recorded in the sliding window mentioned by [Bian et al. (2018)], but the abrupt decline in similarity as well, as in-between instances do not hold the strong requirement of being strongly connected nodes within a community. They rather are points that get passed along the way by the walkers that belong to bordering nodes of the communities that are connected via this one particular node. This distinction also allows a good separation from regular outliers, which, in a fully connected graph, would only get visited by walkers of their respectively nearest community.

After a more in-depth examination of the *minimum inefficiency subgraph* problem [Ruchansky et al. (2017)], we now direct our attention towards the handling of outliers and, more precisely, the ability of the **mis** algorithm to identify in-between instances.

Figure 3.7. Performance of the **mis** algorithm under the aspects of solution size, community detection and outlier handling on large data sets [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]

The second plot in 3.7 depicts the performance of the algorithm in regards to the number of connected components (CC , plotted on the Y-axis) in relation to the number of communities k on the X-axis. From the resulting graphs it is easy to determine that the algorithm is in almost all cases able to detect the number of different communities, shown by the fact that almost all plots are within acceptable margins of the diagonal [Ruchansky et al. (2017)] however there seem to be some settings and circumstances where the performance of the algorithm is subject to fluctuation, as seen in the peaks and valleys of the topmost orange and blue plots.

Focusing on the rightmost plot which represents the **mis**-algorithm performance in regards to outlier detection, with the number of singleton vertices on the Y-axis and an amount of m outliers selected from k different communities [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]. Here it is observed again that the plots, for the most part, follow a nearly linear trend, pointing towards the successful identification and separation of outlier vertices [Ruchansky et al. (2017)].

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Figure 3.8. Exemplary performance of three algorithms on data from the foodpairing-network, with the query vertices being shown in blue and the in-between vertices being colourless circles [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]

To put the performance of the **mis** algorithm into perspective, we take a look at figure 3.8, depicting an example performance of three algorithms we examined in the previous section of this work. The graphs represent the result of a specific task: given a number of (blue) query nodes, add ingredients with a similar chemical flavour profile in order to create a palatable meal, without adding unnecessary or non-fitting ingredients. Whereas the subject of taste and preference when it comes to cooking being a very personal one, it is undeniable that the leftmost result of the **mis** algorithm performs better than the other two algorithms, only adding one connecting ingredient while simultaneously disregarding ingredients as outliers whose flavour profiles are too dissimilar from the other ones in order to be considered fitting additions. The other approaches either only focus on a very small number of the query vertices they were prompted with or add too many connecting vertices with a disregard for cohesiveness across the flavour profile.

It is in this example of the **mis** algorithm that we can identify what we classify as a notion of in-betweenness with one clear differentiating factor from what we have seen in 3.2 - here, the in-between node is picked from the number of non-query nodes of the underlying graph structure and some of the query nodes are regarded as outliers whereas in 3.2 none of the query nodes were treated as outliers in favour of a more well-fitting solution. It is this approach that we would like to see pursued in further works, as this seems to be the most promising way forward concerning this algorithmic approach, a notion that is solidified by two additional case studies in the works of [Ruchansky et al. (2017)].

In the following part we will examine the performance of *FocusCO*, the core point of the paper by [Perozzi et al. (2014)] we already briefly summarised in the previous section of this thesis. The authors have chosen to evaluate the performance of their approach by comparing it to two other graph partitioning algorithms, namely *CODA* and *METIS*. Both methods however only partition the entire graph and do not perform focused cluster extraction, leading to the need for a manual evaluation of the result. Furthermore, other than *FocusCO*, both *CODA* and *METIS* require the number of clusters to return as an input parameter, which disqualifies them from the task of multi-community detection. Additionally, *METIS* neither handles attributes, requiring on a sole focus on graph structure and a workaround in the form of weighting edges with a parameter β via the attribute similarity of their end nodes [Perozzi et al. (2014)]. *CODA* however is capable of performing clustering tasks on attribute graphs, it requires an additional parameter λ to "control the trade-off between structural and attribute similarity of the nodes" [Perozzi et al. (2014)].

Omitting the performance evaluation of *FocusCO* vs. *CODA* and *METIS*, we instead focus on the evaluation of the task of outlier detection, which is beyond the scope of *METIS*, leading to a comparison

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with *CODA* only, which needs yet another parameter r , which marks what percentage of nodes should be returned as outliers.

Figure 3.9. Comparison of *FocusCO* and *METIS* with regards of outlier detection with varying input parameters λ and r , showing the F1-score in the left, and the precision score in the right graph [Perozzi et al. (2014)]

In 3.9 [Perozzi et al. (2014)] analyse the performance of their algorithm with regards of its capability to identify what they deem severe outliers - nodes that deviate "in a larger number of focus attributes from its cluster members". Naturally, these outliers should be easy to detect, which is underlined by the above average performance of the *FocusCO* algorithm. While the X-axis shows the number of deflated focus attributes, meaning the attributes of the cluster that get erased in the outlier to make it a more severe outlier, the Y-axis of the left-hand side plot depicts the F1-score and the Y-axis on the right-hand side plot the precision values of the plot, averaged over 100 runs [Perozzi et al. (2014)]. As expected, the more attributes get depleted, the higher the performance evaluation of the *FocusCO* algorithm, whereas the same trend is not emerging with *CODA*, which the authors explain with *CODAs* inability to calibrate to attribute subspaces.

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Figure 3.10. Disney-centered focus cluster, representing the variety of focus attributes at the top, with the three most desired properties highlighted and the emerging clusters shown below [Perozzi et al. (2014)]

To show the capability of the *FocusCO* algorithm to perform the task we are interested in - the possible identification of in-between instances or at least inadvertent potential thereof, we focus on a real-life application. 3.10. In this, the user sets out with a specific goal in mind: understanding how the popularity of a movie is influential regarding the co-purchases of other related movies in its cluster, therefore assigning a high level of importance to the attributes of overall review number and sales rank, since they are good indicators for the overall popularity of a movie. As a next step, the user themselves picks out a few movies with high values in the desired attributes, revealing a third attribute that seems to stand in relation to the user-determined ones, however without being explicitly set; in this specific case the number of different authors that worked on the various titles. We can see an example of in-between instances with the help of this example in the graphic 3.10, where the blue and orange clusters appear in the same area of the graph. Furthermore, they are also made up of a lot of the same nodes and even share an outlier in the form of "A very Goofy Movie". In order for this similarity in the communities to happen, there need to be some nodes present that link both of these clusters together, which fulfills our understanding of in-betweenness in the scope of this work. With these input parameters, [Perozzi et al. (2014)] extract three different clusters from the graph of Disney movies, the blue one in the leftmost part of the image 3.10 represents the "traditional classics", the green community at the bottom left corner of the graphic symbolises popular older movies, with the final orange cluster on the right side of the image summarising movies that star animated animal protagonists. Of note here is that the orange and blue cluster, described first and last, have noticeable overlap, and that the orange and green cluster even share the same outlier of "An Extremely Goofy Movie".

Extrapolating from these examples, it is fair to assume that *FocusCO*, even though [Perozzi et al.

(2014)], never even consider the possibility, can be a useful tool in the identification of in-between instances, given its strong capability to identify outliers as seen in 3.9, but also in its ability to extract and visualise multiple distinct clusters from the same underlying structure as seen in 3.10. However, challenges arise from their strong emphasis on user-guided focus clusters and weights. If the users are not domain experts in the field of clusters they are trying to extract, it can be exceedingly difficult to spot possible overlaps, assign the correct feature weights to the right nodes and afterwards, come to the right conclusions. If the executing users however are knowledgeable in the field that is visualised by the graph and its nodes, the *FocusCO* algorithm by [Perozzi et al. (2014)] can prove to be a very helpful tool.

In the previous section of this chapter, we already elaborated to some extent on where we see a strong connection and usefulness of the minimum Wiener connector approach as presented by [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]. To further elaborate on the connection we see to our topic of in-between instances and to visualise one of its many use-case scenarios, we examine a real-life example:

Figure 3.11. Depiction of a minimum Wiener connector of a Protein-Protein-Interaction (PPI) network that links genes associated with cancer and Alzheimer's disease. [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]

In this excerpt of a Protein-Protein-Interaction (PPI) network, the authors [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] clearly highlight the use-case of identifying not only vertices with high betweenness-centrality, but especially also the ones we call in-betweeners, that act as linking components between the diseases here. The exploration of these links is not trivial, since it can foster a deeper understanding and even the discovery of entirely new protein-disease associations and the relationship between seemingly unrelated diseases that, after a closer look, are not so disconnected after all [Ruchansky et al. (2015)]. It is clear that this conclusion fits well with our original problem setting - the discovery of the existence of a notion of in-betweenness in already existing approaches. The minimum Wiener connector approach fits particularly well, since its aim is, among others, to find few central vertices that foster a more coherent connection of the existing query vertices. In this real-life example of 3.11, which has been validated against ground-truths provided by previous research into this particular PPI-network, [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] analyse the disease-association of the next step in the connector. This reveals a high connectivity of the inner nodes in this image, leading to the assumption that a close relationship between cancer and Alzheimer's exist, as can be seen by the interconnectedness of proteins such as *p53* and *GSK3B*, with the first one being widely regarded as a central identifier for cancer and the latter one having a non-deniable link to Alzheimer's disease.

We agree with the authors in their statement that finding structures like this, "identifying not only high betweenness and important nodes, but also those that act as links" [Ruchansky et al. (2015)], is of

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vital importance. Our understanding of in-between instances is exactly that: finding the missing links between seemingly unrelated communities of vertices in graphs to reveal and uncover their hidden connections and with that, broadening the way towards understanding their relation to other topics.

3.2. The Notion of In-Between Instances

Table 3.1. Summary of the works examined in this thesis, their understanding of outliers and the notion of in-between instances extractable from their work.

Source	Type of Graph	Notion of Outliers	Types of Outliers	Notion of In-Betweenness
[Ruchansky et al. (2017)]	undirected graph	outlier: graph w.o. selective connector	No differentiation	"relaxing the connectedness allows the connector to detect multiple communities and be tolerant to outliers"
	query vertices			
	subgraph with good cohesiveness properties			
[Bian et al. (2018)]	undirected	no assumption about which target community a query node belongs to	outliers are community- and walker-specific	Nodes that appear in the scope of different random walkers that span more than one target community are a step towards what we see as in-betweenness
	connected	no assumption about the total number of different communities		cosine similarity between score vectors corresponding to query nodes that cross over into other communities can be a good tool for identification
[Perozzi et al. (2014)]	large attribute graphs	"clusters and outliers are [...] mined according to [...] user preference"	determined by the focused cluster they are structurally connected to	the FocusCO algorithm is able to detect overlapping communities and their outliers
	attribute weights	"a node that belongs to a focused cluster structurally, but that deviates from its members in some focus attributes significantly is an outlier"	even attributes with high attribute weights can be outliers	however the algorithm is strongly reliant on a domain expert to recognize the overlap in focus attributes
	exemplary nodes			

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Table 3.2. Continued summary of the works examined in this thesis, their understanding of outliers and the notion of in-between instances extractable from their work.

Source	Type of Graph	Notion of Outliers	Types of Outliers	Notion of In-Betweenness
[Ruchansky et al. (2015)]	undirected, connected, unweighted graph			"the additional vertices needed to form the connector will "contain vertices adjacent to edges that bridge the different communities"
	parameter free			"Identifying [...] high betweenness and important nodes, [and] also those that act as links, gives potential for new directions of investigation[...]. The connector also provides a concise summary of the relationships that is amenable to visualization."

Conclusion and Future Work

4.1 Conclusion

In this paper we introduced the differentiation between 'simple' outliers versus in-between instances on graphs - those nodes that, although their connection to their respective communities might not be as strong as the one of its original query vertices, are of particular strategic and informational value. It is interesting to see that all of the examined approaches in the previous chapter of this work already show an at least basic understanding of this importance, be it [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] who state that "Identifying [...] high betweenness and important nodes, [and] also those that act as links, gives potential for new directions of investigation[...]" or [Bian et al. (2018)] who come to the conclusion that nodes that appear in the scope of different random walkers that span more than one target community are of high value in locating these communities. However none of the examined approaches we elaborated on in this work ever take a step back to consider the meaning of their findings in the context of treating these nodes different than either some type of outlier.

One critical aspect that all of the presented approaches have in common is their inherent capability to identify multiple communities. This capacity is vital, since for the true power of in-between instances - bridging a gap between different communities and creating links between related, but separated communities - we need more than one cluster in the underlying graph to begin with. It is important to note here that those clusters should never be created for the sake of having more than one cluster only, since that would never lead to sensible results. Another takeaway from this work is the strong assumption that the task of in-betweenness detection is possible on a large variety of different graphs. In this thesis alone we came across undirected ([Bian et al. (2018), [Ruchansky et al. (2017)]) as well as attribute graphs ([Perozzi et al. (2014)], presented a parameter-free approach in the form of [Ruchansky et al. (2015)] and a wide variety of real-life examples, ranging from social network graphs as seen in 3.4 and 3.3, Protein-Protein-Interactions like 3.11 and even chemical flavour profile networks of food 3.8. This allows us to come to the conclusion that our task of identifying in-between instances in graphs as well is not bound by the type of data, but has the potential to be applicable to a wide range of different use-cases, both of real-world and artificial conception. Another interesting albeit not unexpected observation made is that the methods we examined operate under different optimisation objectives whose single combining denominator is the criterion that the solutions obtained not be of arbitrarily large size but instead as small as possible. Additionally to that, all methods differ in their primary optimisation goal, an unsurprising observation since the same holds true for other tasks like clustering itself, with *k-means* optimising with regards of variance and *EM* optimises with regards of the best possible fit.

Another conclusion we came to in the scope of this work is that a good amount of the applications examined already show a potential for the identification on in-betweenness, even if this was hitherto not the intention or even on the mind of the respective authors.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

4.2 Future Work

In the future, we would like to see an implementation of an algorithm that has the capability of achieving the following things: given a graph $G = (V, E)$ and a set of query vertices Q ,

1. have the capacity to identify multiple communities
2. identify the vertices that connect communities
3. add those in-between vertices and the connected community to the solution space
4. find a solution that is minimally small without obfuscating any important connections or vertices
5. find this solution in a reasonable amount of time and efficiency

Furthermore, we would like to expand this survey into the prevalence of in-betweenness in existing research, literature and methods, albeit under the guise of different names or even as an unnamed side occurrence as we have seen with all of the papers examined in this work.

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